

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PREPARATION FOR FAMILY LIFE AS A REQUIREMENT THAT IMPROVES STUDENT PERSONALITY

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ABSTRACT

The development of society is ensured by the activities of people who have a normal personality, and a normal family environment ensures the normal formation of the personality. In this regard, ensuring the factors that determine the integrity and strength of the family is considered one of the most urgent and global problems of interest to the society.

The role of young people in society, the trends and perspectives of their development are of great interest to society and are of practical importance. Because young people determine the future of society. Here, young people's attitude towards marriage and family, preparation for family life plays an important role. This process is a requirement for improving the personality of the young generation. In order for the result to be successful, pre-school institutions, secondary and higher schools, extra-curricular institutions, the public, radio and television, the press, society in general, and the state must provide their assistance.

Keywords: young generation, family life, self-awareness, gender problem, behavioral ethics.

Introduction

Family is a social phenomenon that accompanies a person throughout his life. Family is not the coexistence of people belonging to several age groups, but also the coexistence of people in mutual harmony. The family is a small state, which means that the family, as the main core of society, must be built on a solid foundation. This foundation is spiritual, psychological, physiological, self-awareness, mutual respect and love, sense of responsibility, family rights, duties, etc. It is further strengthened when it is built on the principles of high preparation and understanding of aspects. Thus, if young boys and girls start a family early before they reach the age of maturity, and at the same time, when the psychological, spiritual, and physiological preparation processes of both individuals are not properly organized in the period before the family life, the mistake in the process of responsibility and self-awareness is the beginning of the path to the destruction of the family. The importance of purposeful preparation of young students for family life is determined by the further development of family-marital relations. Because the comprehensive and harmonious development of the personality formed in the family directly depends on the establishment of family relations in a positive direction. This process similarly affects the mutual relations between men and women in family life.

Preparation of student youth for family life will have a positive effect on the improvement of their personal qualities, and at the same time, it will help to reduce the number of incomplete families in the society.

The main part

The family plays a major role in shaping the identity of the young generation and preparing them for social life.

“Family does not mean a room where any person lives. Here feelings, interests, a favorite place where family members are always expected, a place where those who love, understand each other and defend each other live” [5, p. 416].

“Family is an institution belonging to a group of people, distinguished by its own rules and a closed way of life within society, built on kinship relations” [6, p. 9].

“The family is one of the primary forms of social unity of the society, which includes the couple and their children. Family performs reproductive, educational, economic, psychological functions of important importance for society” [2, p. 51].

In the family, the child gains the first experience of interpersonal relationships. Here the foundations of his life position are laid. No other social institution can be compared to the family in terms of the influence and duration of the family in the formation of a person as a personality. No state, no cultural society can exist and survive without family. The future and development of the country and the state depend on strong and successful families.

Work in the direction of preparing the young generation for family life has always been in the center of attention. Each of the concepts of family, marriage and love has its own role in the life and development of society and people. Love is the moral basis of the family, and marriage is the legal basis. These aspects should be taken into account when preparing the young generation - student youth for family life.

In preparing young people for independent family life and marriage, the main focus should be on the spiritual and psychological aspects of family relations. The main issue in this field is the moral-psychological aspect of the relations between the sexes. In addition, student boys and girls should familiarize themselves with the basics of family and marriage legislation, develop confidence in the fairness of relevant normative acts, create a need to fulfill them and instill in them the ability to form a responsible attitude to the legal basis of the family - marriage. The work on preparing students for marriage, family life and raising their future children is directed towards synthesizing different aspects

of education. This work attracts attention with its spiritual, legal, physical, medical, pedagogical, and especially psychological features. As much as it is important for young people to love each other, enter into a marriage union, and start a family, both the family and the society are interested in this love being deep, the marriage successful, and the family strong.

In non-auditory events, where appropriate, attention should be paid to the moral, psychological, legal and economic foundations of the family, interpersonal relations, including the proper organization of mutual relations between spouses, parents and children. The moral and psychological climate of the family, the rights and duties of the husband and wife, the moral and legal duty they bear to the family and society, the responsibilities of parents in relation to their children, etc. should be covered with necessary knowledge and information. If students are helped to find the right answers to the questions of whom to marry and whom to marry, the purity of mutual relations between male and female students, the further development of friendship and companionship, sharing each other's joys and sorrows, respecting each other's feelings of love, if concern for each other's fate, concern for each other's concerns is typical for each academic group and the student body of the higher school in general, students will become a family they can be successfully prepared for life and the education of their future children. Young people's wrong steps in choosing a spouse leave their parents, and parents' inappropriate intervention puts young people in front of a choice, creates a number of problems and difficulties. In the first case, parents, in the second case, young people or one of them suffers psychological trauma. All this shows that along with schoolchildren, a well-thought-out activity system and work system for preparing students for marriage and family life should be created.

Banality in relationships between young men and women, irresponsibility in intimate relationships, sexual crimes, increasing number of divorces, etc. such issues are the result of the lack of active psychological and pedagogical theory and practice.

The breakup of families is caused by a number of reasons. This includes the inability of spouses to adapt to each other from a psychological point of view, joint life, in other words, the lack of features that are important for living together "under one roof", the interference of outsiders in the life of the family, the difficulty of making a living, the inability to find a job, the psychological condition of men and women. inability to adapt, having different types of temperament, sexual incompatibility, neglect of one of the parents towards the upbringing of children, family economy, livelihood, infidelity and jealousy situations, striving for leadership in the family, etc. includes Economic, psychological, alcoholism, drug addiction, immorality of spouses, sometimes interference of parents or relatives from both sides in the family life, husband and wife going abroad, or not being at home for a long time in order to earn money also cause divorce. Of course, if young people develop a serious attitude towards independent family life, love, marriage, and family, and if they are taught the ability to raise children, a number of reasons

listed above will disappear in the future. From this point of view, the role of spiritual and psychological preparation is great. Such preparation helps young people to have the right attitude to the issue of gender and sexual relations between people, etc. implies.

Self-awareness, self-education and self-evaluation have a special role in preparing young people for family life and marriage. Prof. Q.E.Azimov writes: "Self-awareness, which is one of the most important dimensions of human honor, human dignity and personality, is neither inherited nor instilled from the outside. For this, every person must work regularly and intensely on his own effort, his own hard work, his own hard work and will, it is required to mobilize the power of his mind and intelligence. Each personality should be closely involved in his own upbringing, and should work on his character regularly and insistently. Without it, it is impossible to become a perfect person. One must always look inside oneself, if one is not aware of one's inner world, one cannot understand one's existence. Self-awareness one necessity is that it allows each of us to see the qualities that are unique to us that no one else can see that it seems to shine a light, allowing a person to see what is there clearly and, as a result, self-awareness, opening the way for a person to think about himself in a healthy way. Such common sense directs a person to stay away from mistakes" [4, p. 319-321]. There is deep truth in the author's words. It is also possible to attribute them to work on preparation for family life.

Preparation for independent family life, family-marriage relations depends very much on organizing self-education of young students and forming their demand for self-education. Self-discipline is necessary in adolescence and youth, as well as in family life. We live among people. Our every step, our deed is always reflected to some extent in the lives of other people - our spouse, children, relatives and acquaintances. Therefore, each of us should educate ourselves to be a good person, companion, friend, and finally have a family. The higher the level of education of a person, the more self-report, self-control, self-analysis, self-observation, self-responsibility, self-evaluation, self-instruction, etc. the more well-formed he is, the more he will correctly evaluate other people, will not play with their feelings, will understand their situation, joy, sadness, and in addition to self-awareness, he will also understand others in a way. All this applies to the relationship between husband and wife, and this is one way to prepare for family life.

"The level of spiritual awareness of young people plays an important role in preparing for family life. The development of moral consciousness by young boys and girls is based on the understanding of the social value of the family, a serious attitude towards the marriage union, a sense of responsibility for the created family, choosing a life partner wisely, having deep respect for the future husband (wife), his parents and relatives, polite and intelligent behavior and sensitivity, sincerity and kindness, caring and kindness, as well as being able to properly establish mutual relations and communication with them, pleasant manifests itself in behavior" [1, p. 180].

One of the main issues in preparing students for marriage and family life is the establishment of correct mutual relations between the sexes. "What should be the relationship between young men and women?" to the question, A.S.Makarenko expressed his attitude as follows: "A sincere, genuine relationship is such that nothing is exaggerated or minimized. Relationships are healthy when they do not deceive each other, when they respect themselves and others, it does not depend on how these relationships are oriented towards friendship, love, etc".

The psychological problems of preparing students for marriage and family life are closely related to the problems of gender, including issues of gender equality, which are included in science as "gender problems" in modern times. "Gender" is a multifaceted concept. It includes sex, its rights and duties, freedoms, as well as separate areas of intersex relations. "Gender" means sex in English. If there is no sense of equality of rights, mutual debt and responsibility in family relations, there will be psychological comfort in the family, satisfaction with family life, etc. it is not possible. Gender equality creates favorable conditions for improving the psychological climate of the family.

In order to become good heads of families, good husbands and wives, good parents, and most importantly, good citizens in the future, young people should learn the ethics of behavior and communication ethics. Every young man should consider his sexual behavior. Every boy and girl should know how to give a flower, how to receive a guest, how to meet them. When going up or down the stairs, the man should walk in front. If a woman asks something or gives information about something, a man should stand and listen to her carefully. When getting into a taxi, the man should open the car door and help the woman. There are many rules of conduct and etiquette. Etiquette can also be formal in nature. Therefore, it is difficult to talk about a person's communication culture based only on external signs.

The word "etiquette" is originally derived from the word "ethics". Behavioral labels are essentially related to moral principles and moral values.

It is these principles that are most necessary in relationships between boys and girls, men and women. People have always attached great importance to moral principles in communication culture and still do. The culture of communication is expressed in the inner beauty of human relationships. Politeness, restraint, principles, compromise, kindness, kindness, the ability to listen to the other party and the desire to understand, to respect his taste and opinions, to understand his joy and sorrow, and to be heartbroken and share in his pain, these are the alphabet of culture. Everyone should learn and master this alphabet. In this sense, communication culture is related to the concept of "educated person". A well-educated person is a person who considers the interests of others, takes them into account in his behavior and attitude, and faces every difficulty on his way. We should approach the issue of the importance of communication culture in personal relationships from this point of view. The culture of communication between a boy and a girl should show itself in all areas

of their personal life, first of all in their intimate relationships. K.Marx considered a man's relationship with a woman to be an indicator of the general culture of society. Kind, polite, sensitive people act like this in the intimate sphere as well. They find a way to the heart of the girl they love, they don't care about her in the slightest, they don't humiliate her with an inappropriate word or action, they protect her reputation, honor and modesty like the apple of an eye. A lot depends on the girl herself in these relationships. She should never forget that she will be a mother, she should ennoble her future wife with her actions throughout her life, and she should treat him and herself with moral standards.

According to psychologists, during the preparation of young people for an independent family life, the creation of the following relationships in them is considered a serious psychological task:

- ✓by itself as the subject of conscious moral behavior

- ✓to members of the opposite sex

- ✓family, to family relations, to himself as a future husband (wife) and father (mother).

- ✓to understand personal sex life, its nature, its nature and importance for human health and social behavior

All this has a moral orientation and is closely related to the world surrounding students and their life experience.

Self-attitude involves a number of interrelated components. First of all, this means the attitude towards oneself as a subject, the attitude towards one's behavior and activities, understanding one's role and place in life. It means responsibility to oneself, relatives, collective and family of which it is a member. In addition, it includes his personal qualities, character traits, correct evaluation of them, desire (unwillingness) to improve them or get rid of defects. Also, it is intended to make decisions and act freely, to try to be independent.

Relationships between parents, students' personal relationships, press, public environment, student audience, higher school staff, mass media, cinema, theater, television shows influence the attitude towards representatives of the opposite sex. Under the influence of various situations, this relationship is not correct at all, in some cases it comes down to the level of intimate relationships only. Variants of this attitude among students are different: neglect, not understanding one's responsibility, playing with the feelings of the opposite sex, using the inexperience of the opposite sex, deliberately deceiving, being mistaken in one's feelings, not having the necessary information about the psychological and moral foundations of intersex (interpersonal) interactions, etc.

In a number of cases, young people's attitudes to family issues are corrected based on the relationships prevailing in their families, on the basis of examples taken from literary works, theater and cinema, and television programs based on the life examples of famous people they meet.

As for the attitude of young students to intimate life, it should be noted that this issue depends, first of all, on the attitude of the elderly to the problem and how the people around them evaluate the moral foundations

of intimate life. Ignorance, vulgarity, frankness, lack of self-reporting, lack of self-restraint, inability to self-evaluate create the ground for a crude and naked sexual interpretation of this important issue. Therefore, purposeful work among students should help to reveal the essence of love, family and family relationships.

Society has always been interested in the issue of preparing the growing generation, including young people, for independent family life and raising their future children. First of all, the family took on that responsibility. This is due to several reasons:

- to inculcate work skills and habits in children, to prepare helpers for the work that father and mother must perform in the family farm and household; to take care of the psychological, spiritual and physical health of their children (the human body is strengthened in the labor process);

- to instill the necessary knowledge and skills in homemaking, family farming and family life, to be able to create a normal psychological and spiritual climate in one's family, to take care of a child, to engage in educational work, etc.

The foundations of the child's formation as a future man and woman are also laid in the family. It is necessary to pay special attention to this issue. There are certain customs and traditions in child upbringing. When raising boys and girls in the family, they usually expect these customs and traditions. Each parent takes into account standards and stereotypes of masculinity and femininity established in the society, instills in boys the specific needs, interests and character traits, customs and habits, behavior and behavior rules for boys and for girls.

Psychological studies show that girls acquire the standards of femininity, first of all, in the context of dialogue (communication) with their mothers. In accordance with these standards, they are inculcated with the habits of homemaking and taking care of children, musical culture (including playing a lullaby), a sense of respect for a man in the example of one's father and brothers, and the tact of dealing with boys. They have kindness, restraint, politeness, etc. special attention is paid to the formation of typical qualities for a girl. Male children are instilled with male character traits, especially willful qualities. They have restraint, endurance, courage, etc. qualities are nurtured. A boy should be treated with respect to women and girls by the example of his mother and sister, help them in difficult tasks, etc. is grafted. More attention is paid to their physical education.

Parents' behavior is also important in children's adoption of male and female roles. The example of a father as a man and a mother as a woman is equally necessary in the formation of children as boys and girls. In this regard, the nature of parents' attitude towards their children is also important.

The preparation of the growing generation for family life depends to a great extent on the level of sex education, and it also leaves its traces in family-marital relations. One of the main reasons for the breakdown of family-marital relations is related to the fact that the parties - men and women - are not aware of each other's

psychological characteristics. This hinders mutual understanding, and in some cases, conflicts between the parties create conditions for the disintegration of the family.

A.Y. Verb considers the study of the sexual characteristics of the younger generation important in two ways. These are: 1) ensuring proper level of male-female relations in social life; 2) ensures the preparation of the growing generation for family life.

Although the sexual, psychological and social maturity of boys and girls do not correspond to each other chronologically, they are always formed in relation to each other. In order to correctly understand the role of sexual maturation processes in adolescence and early youth, this issue is of fundamental importance. Sexual orientation, which appears as a necessary result of sexual development, becomes relevant in such a situation that the psychological and social factors determining the personality of boys and girls are of great importance. They develop new psychological characteristics, especially the feeling of old age. Sexual orientation is included in the structure of those psychological characteristics, it participates together with them, not separately, in the formation of attitudes towards the opposite sex. In other words, personality development becomes a leading and determining factor for the entire process of mental development during adolescence. Thus, sexual orientation begins to take on a mediated character. Its content changes qualitatively: It becomes psychologized and manifests itself as sexual interest, a psychological phenomenon, gradually taking the form of human love in the process of its development. In mutual relations between boys and girls, spiritual closeness and personality aspects begin to play an important role.

All these aspects, of course, should be taken into account in the preparation of young students for family life.

R.I. Aliyev devoted his research to the consideration of national characteristics in the formation of the student's personality and the determination of ethno-psychological bases of personality formation. Although the author does not set out to study the problem of the independent family life of the young generation, he expresses his attitude to these issues when appropriate, and draws attention to the close connection of that field with national characteristics. R.I. Aliyev "What qualities do you like or would you like to see in your husband (fiancé)?" addressed men (boys) and women (girls) with his question. Let's pay attention to the results: "45% of women said that they want to be able to earn money in the first place, understand them in the second place, 29% said that they want to be married in the first place, in the second place they want to be able to earn money, and in the third place they want to be educated. And 15% of women in the first place, they indicated that their husbands were educated, in the second place, the spiritual and psychological closeness, and in the third place, 11% indicated that they could earn wealth they already considered giving opinions, they accepted their husbands (fiancés) as they are, and said that destiny was given by God.

Among the qualities that 73% of men want to see in women, they put family life, being able to support them morally, education in the second place, beauty and neatness in the third place. 19% put helping a man in the family's livelihood in the first place, understanding him, taking care of the family in the second place, being neat and attractive in the third place, education in the fourth place, and 8% said that they did not pay attention to such issues" [3, p. 97-98].

The purpose of the author in conducting such a survey was to reveal the compatibility and incompatibility between the attitudes of young boys and girls, men and women towards the family, and the views of the parties that make up the family. Moral and psychological numbness or disharmony, unity of opinion, disagreement decides the fate of the family in a positive or negative direction.

It is also recommended to consider national characteristics in preparing young people for family life. It is necessary to study the ideas of the young generation about ideal female and male images and guide teenagers and young people. The idea of ideal female and male images is a regulator of the morale and behavior of boys and girls, and determines their attitude towards their peers of the opposite sex. For this very reason, the formation of female and male character, conceptions of femininity and masculinity is one of the main conditions in the sexual education of boys and girls.

As it is known, sexual education plays an important role in preparing teenagers and young people for family life. Without conducting sexual education, without taking into account sexual characteristics, without knowing the psychological characteristics of social development, male and female sex representatives, the characteristics of sexual development and sexual maturity, it is difficult to effectively establish work on preparation for family life.

In the article, the duties of work on preparation for family life have also been clarified. It is shown that the efforts to prepare young people for the roles they will play in the future should be focused on cultivating qualities such as good heads of families, family owners, housewives, fathers and mothers, grooms and brides, husbands and wives. For this boys and girls:

- they should be able to choose a worthy life partner for themselves, they should be morally and psychologically ready to get married, start a family, raise their future children;

- they should be able to create conditions of sincere, kind, mutual respect in the family, be loyal to the ideal, make compromises when necessary, and ensure cultural relaxation of the family;

- in the future, they should be surrounded by the necessary knowledge and skills for the healthy birth of their children, their normal development and upbringing;

- they should acquire the relevant skills to organize the family economy and budget;

- they should wait for the tact of the relationship with new relatives, try to strengthen family ties, etc.

Conclusion

I can note that there is an influence of standards and stereotypes in society on the formation of ideas about the family life of young students. Taking national and moral values into account in the preparation of young people for family life determines the success of this process. Eliminating negative situations that have a negative impact on family life is analogously related to the process of forming young people's ideas about family and marriage culture in the context of family values.

In particular, students acquire pedagogical and psychological knowledge in connection with the teaching of pedagogy and psychology subjects in pedagogically oriented institutes and universities compared to other higher schools. These subjects create a clear idea of the effective ways, principles and methods of preparing for family life and raising children. Preparing the young generation for family life should be an important issue of social development.

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